

MODELLING OF HIGH VELOCITY IMPACT ON WOVEN FABRICS AND COMPOSITE MATERIALS

C. Navarro

Department of Materials Science
Polytechnic University of Madrid
Ciudad Universitaria s/n
28040-Madrid (Spain)

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a résumé of the different engineering methodologies to solve the problem of impact of solids at high velocity on fabrics and fibre-reinforced polymeric matrix composites. Some of the main differences between low and high velocity impact regimes are detailed. The influence of the parameters characterizing the composite, such as the resin content, fabric architecture, etc., are also considered. Particular attention is paid to the phenomenological models -engineering models- normally used to treat ballistic impact problems. The advantages and disadvantages of the various models are briefly discussed, with their main characteristics and assumptions. Results of several full-numerical analyses are also included.

Keywords: Impact, Ballistics, Fabrics, Composites, Ceramics, Armour design.

1. INTRODUCTION

In many engineering problems the possibility of impact on a structure, system or component should be considered as another design load hypothesis alongside the conventional ones. Such are the cases of a spacecraft, in which meteoroid impact may occur, or an aircraft engine, where a fan blade can be released for any unforeseen reason, impacting against the engine containment, or crashworthiness capabilities for passengers safety in automotive vehicles, etc.. In the military industry there are also many applications involving impact phenomena: protection of infantry fighting vehicles against low velocity-high energy impacting solids, which can occur when maneuvering the vehicle, or against high velocity-high energy impacting projectiles; impact problems on helicopters, etc., and finally in personal armour protection (for instance, helmets and bullet-proof vests). All these problems have a common characteristic: the armour protection against impact should be as light as possible in order to avoid the loss of mobility of the protected structures or persons. This is the key aspect of the problem: armour weight versus achieved protection.

Composite materials are suitable for use in the problems involving high velocity impact because they combine lightness with high mechanical strength. In some special cases, e.g. ballistic impact of medium caliber projectiles travelling at high velocity, in which composite materials are not sufficiently resistant to impact loading, they are used in conjunction with ceramics, to prevent armour perforation while allowing a global weight save of the armour.

This paper deals with the modelling of the impact of projectiles on fibres, fabrics, composite materials and composite materials faced by ceramic tiles. Several calculation tools have been considered so far for design purposes: those based on empirical formulations, obtained after numerous real fire tests; those founded on engineering simulation of the micro and macro-mechanical

material behaviours present on the impact event, and finally those based on numerical analysis of the problem. Traditionally, most of the engineering approaches have been developed using analytical models, but they are normally computer-based and thus they become more numerical than analytical tools.

2. RESISTANCE OF LAMINATES AGAINST IMPACT

As is well known, the impact problems on composite materials can be grouped into low and high velocity impact regimes. Usually, the kind of impact regime to be considered depends on the velocity of the impactor and thus of its kinetic energy. Although a boundary between such regimes can not be clearly defined, it would be convenient to establish the order of magnitude of the impactor kinetic energy in several practical problems. In the low velocity impact regime, kinetic energies range from zero up to, say, a very few hundred joules. In ballistic impact of small caliber ammunition, the projectile kinetic energy ranges from 700 J (9 mm Pb. NATO projectile) to 3,100 J (7,62 mm NATO projectile). In a large fan engine, for instance, a released blade might have a kinetic energy of up to 230,000 J [1]. That is, the kinetic energy range in which a composite structure can be subjected to impact loading may reach, depending on the type of impact considered, up to several thousand joules. From a phenomenological description of the impact event on composite materials, the differences between the low and the high velocity impact regimes can be based on the type of composite response. For instance, carbon fibre-reinforced plastic materials present very different behaviours at low and high velocity impact [9]. At low velocity impact, the structural geometry characteristics of the target determine its impact response because the elastic energy absorbing capability of the target is the main factor. Note that the contact time between the impactor and the target is long and thus elastic and plastic waves have time enough to travel into the whole target material, mobilizing its full-impact strength. However, for high velocity impact in which the duration of the event is much shorter, the geometry of the target, such as its length, width, shape, etc., is less important because the target response is now localized around the impact point. Although the damage area can be apparently smaller in the high velocity impact regime (for example, in ballistic impact), the loss of residual integrity of a composite armour after impact is greater than in the former case. Another important difference between the impact regimes concerns the post-impact behaviour of the composite material structural element: in the majority of cases, after low velocity impact, the composite material element should be capable of bearing further stresses and it must preserve its structural integrity whereas, in high velocity impact conditions, such as those of ballistic impact, the damage to the composite material structural element is irreversible, and it must be removed and substituted by another.

The impact resistance of a laminate composite depends on several factors: fibre properties (titre, elastic moduli, viscoelastic properties and failure strain), fibre architecture (unidirectional fibres, woven fabrics, etc.), matrix resin properties, composite areal density, etc.. Conventional static properties of composite materials and the corresponding test devices are well known but, the dynamic properties of composite materials at high strain rates is now a hot point in the dynamic characterization of materials. Some experimental devices, such as the Charpy pendulum and drop tower tests, have been widely used for this purpose. But in both devices either the impacting energy is too low in comparison with those of high velocity impact, or the specimen is tested only in compressive conditions. Also the strain rate to which the specimen is subjected during the tests may not remain constant. This is a problem because the latter parameter has a very great influence on the behaviour of composite materials and thus should remain constant during the whole test. Important advances in the dynamic characterization of composite materials in tension, compression and interlaminar shear conditions have been carried out by the group of Professors Ruiz and Harding [2], who use the Hopkinson bar test device that permits to test the composite materials at a practically constant strain rate. So, it has been detected that woven carbon fibre/epoxy composites [2], for instance, show a significant increase in the tensile and compressive failure strengths when strain rate increases, although the failure strain diminishes in tension and the interlaminar shear strength increases.

Comparing, for example, the ballistic efficiency of fabric packs and laminates with the same amount of fabric, it has been shown that fabric packs are more effective when soft-core ammunition is involved although such effectiveness is lower for armour piercing projectiles. Also, for projectiles impacting at low velocity, fabric packs have proved to be more effective than laminates, whereas at higher impact velocities the opposite occurs. This means that the energy dissipation mechanisms at low and high impact velocity are quite different. It is also well known that for thermoset matrix composites, and contrary to what occurs in other structural applications of composite materials, the

ballistic resistance to normal impact on a panel seems to decrease as the matrix content is increased. This means that the more flexible the laminate, the greater its ballistic efficiency. So for the case of a fragment simulating projectile of 64 grains (4.147 g) impacting on aramid fabric (6.2 kg/m²), with different resin types (epoxy or vinylester) and different contents, the ballistic limit V₅₀ (velocity at which 50 percent of projectiles penetrate the armour, whereas 50 percent of projectiles are stopped) decreases by about 20 percent for vinylester resin weight contents varying from 10 to 50 percent. This effect can be explained if immediate matrix cracking after impact occurred within the composite plate zone affected by the transversal displacements: the fractured matrix moves together with the fibres without collaborating in bearing stresses, so its effect on the composite response is only inertial [3]. This means that the transversal wave velocity on the composite is slower than on that of the fibre, and thus the zone of the composite plate collaborating in defeating the impactor is also smaller.

Investigations have focused on the low velocity regime, existing a wide bibliography on this subject (the reader is referred to the work of Greszczuk [4], for a more detailed description, and to the work of Shivakumar et al. [5], who developed simplified models for calculating the impact force and duration for low-velocity impact problems). From the work of Greszczuk it seems that the impact resistance of a composite increases as the fibre tenacity increases and the fibre elasticity modulus becomes lower, and as the elasticity modulus of the matrix decreases and the strength of the matrix increases. The major internal failure mechanism of the composite material is related to the matrix cracking and delamination, the maximum delamination showing a linear dependency on the impact energy [6]. Sjöblom et al. [7] showed that for non-rate-sensitive composite materials, static indentation tests could give the same results as a low-velocity impact test for the graphite/epoxy and graphite/semi-crystalline thermoplastic composites involved in their study.

At higher impact velocities, fibre debonding is the failure mechanism of the composite that absorbs less energy, and thus fibre failure parameters become the most important to characterize the composite behaviour, although other failure mechanisms may also appear. So comparing the behaviour of aramid laminates and fabric packs with the same areal density of fibre material, it has been observed that, when impacted by fragment ammunition, they present different ballistic efficiency depending on the impact velocity; that is, fabrics present a higher ballistic limit than laminates at lower impact velocities, whereas the contrary is true at higher velocity. Some work [8] has been devoted to the study of failure mechanisms such as shear plugging, fibre debonding, etc., caused by the impact of a blunt penetrator. Other works [9] show a comparison of the response of CFRP laminates in low and high velocity impact conditions. Experimental research on matrix cracking, delamination zone and wave propagation effects, have been carried out by Takeda et al. [10,11,12,13] for the case of blunt penetrators; Joshi and Sun [14] and Liu and Malvern [15] studied matrix cracking caused by the impact of spherical penetrators; in a deep study, Zhu et al. [16] analyzed the ballistic limits of sharp-pointed projectiles impacting on kevlar/polyester laminates, identifying a square-shaped damage zone for 0/90 lay-up and a circular damage area for quasi-isotropic laminates. They also state a set of important conclusions on the phenomenological description of the ballistic behaviour of the considered laminates: global and shear rigidity of laminate plates, which has an important role in quasi-static penetration, has considerably smaller influence in dynamic penetration; local deformation and fibre failure are the major energy absorption mechanisms in impact perforation; and deliberately introduced delaminations in the laminate do not change the impact strength of the composite panel.

3. ENGINEERING MODELLING

To understand the behaviour of a composite material subjected to high velocity impact it is necessary to consider first the behaviour of a simple fibre when transversely impacted by a projectile, and then the impact behaviour of fabric panels. The problem has been widely analyzed by many authors. In particular, Roylance [17] presented the theoretical bases of the problem, showing that after impact two waves are propagating along the fibre, which presents a V form zone near to the impact point. The faster wave is a tensional wave of magnitude σ , which is propagating at the sound velocity of the fibre material:

$$c = (E/\rho)^{1/2}$$

where E is the elasticity modulus of the fibre and ρ its density. This wave may present a dispersive

character due to non-linear fibre behaviour. In the region behind the tensional wave front, material flows towards the impacted region, at a velocity that depends on the tensional wave speed and on the fibre strain ϵ reached. After this wave, a transversal wave travels at a velocity u which depends on the fibre stress, strain and material density according to:

$$u = [\sigma/(\rho (1+\epsilon))]^{1/2}$$

Behind the transverse wave front, all fibre particles move at a velocity equal in magnitude and direction to that of the projectile.

When a fabric is considered, the situation becomes more complex. This was also analyzed by Roylance [17], who proposed a finite difference discretization to treat the problem, assuming strain rate independent material properties and accounting for the non-linear viscoelastic relaxation of the fibre material [18]; by Vinson and Zukas [19] and by Leech and Adeyefa [20]. Using his numerical method, Roylance studied the influence of the fibre properties on the ballistic behaviour of textile panels [21], stating that the rate of energy absorption of a panel increases monotonically with the fibre modulus, although high modulus materials tend to exhibit a low breaking strain which reduces the impact resistance. He also gave a "master-curve" description of impact response for different panel materials (nylon, aramid and graphite) to minimize the number of full computer simulations necessary to design panels. The interaction between warps and filling fibres at crossovers complicates the dynamic fabric behaviour: the propagating energy is diverted in each cross-over. The effect of crossovers is even more complicated if slippage between fibres is considered. This effect was also analyzed by Roylance [22] who stated that the extension of wave diversion decreases as the fibre modulus gets smaller, and the influence of the crossover also diminishes as the extent of sliding increases. Another important conclusion of Roylance's model is that the most of the energy absorbed by a fabric subjected to normal impact was due to strain and kinetic energy in the fibres in contact with the projectile. The fibre failure criterion assumed by Roylance in all his calculations is that proposed by Zhurkov [23].

Vinson and Zukas [19] proposed modelling a multilayered armour as a conical shell subjected to axially symmetric load although very complex experimental work to obtain some of the parameters required by their model. Leech and Adeyefa [20] employed the method of characteristics, to simulate the dynamics of textile structures subjected to ballistic impact.

More recently, Cunniff [24] presented a very interesting paper in which the ballistic efficiency of woven fabrics is discussed from a conceptual framework developed to relate single impact fibre properties to fabric impact mechanics. He also pointed out that a steep strain gradient appears along fibres in the region of the fabric affected by the transverse deflection.

For the case of impact of projectiles at high speed against composite panels, there are just a few engineering models available in the open literature. One of the easiest would be one based on the previously defined models for impact on fabrics, to which the inertial effect of the cracked matrix would be added according to Morrison and Bader's suggestion [3]. One of the more recent model is that of Zhu et al. [25] who proposed an analytical model based on the laminated plate theory, for the normal impact of conically-tipped hard-steel cylinders on laminated Kevlar/polyester composites. The model accounts for the dissipative mechanisms, fibre failure, delamination, etc., using simplified assumptions. It states three different stages of the penetration process: indentation of the projectile, perforation of the laminate and exit. Resistive forces for each stage were ascertained and Newton's second law gives the response of both projectile and target. Particular attention should be paid to a simplified model proposed by Parga [26] which gives a detailed picture of the penetration process. The model considers the ply-ply interaction and the effect of slippage between warp and filling fibres in the crossovers, proposing an exponentially decreasing law for the yarn stress to account for this last effect. The model considers that the deformation wave propagates at a velocity between those of the fibre and matrix materials, obtained by the following expression:

$$c = c_m + (c_f - c_m) (V_f + K - 1) / K$$

where c is longitudinal elastic wave velocity in the composite material, K the critical resin content determining impact behaviour of the composite (see, for example, reference [27]), c_m the longitudinal elastic wave velocity in the matrix resin, c_f the longitudinal elastic wave velocity in the fibre material and, finally, V_f the volume fraction. As in the model of Zhu et al. [25] the fibre fails when its strain reaches a maximum value.

Another important use of composite materials in impact applications is as the backing plate of ceramic tiles. This kind of mixed armour has shown great ballistic efficiency because of the erosive characteristics of ceramics and its intrinsic lightness as a consequence of the use of composite as a backing plate instead of a metallic one. One of the pioneer works on this subject was that of Maysless et al. [28] who considered the impact of a 12.7 mm diameter hard-steel projectile with 60 deg conical tips (30 g mass) impacting, at normal incidence and different velocities below 250 m/s, several targets made of alumina AD-85 backed by metallic or aramid/polyester composite (K29 Kevlar bonded under pressure with a polyester resin representing 43-47 percent of the final composite volume). In their work, Maysless et al. [28] show that the energy to fracture the ceramic material was negligible compared to that required for projectile erosion and thus this last mechanism played the main role in defeating the projectile. They also observed that for a constant thickness of the ceramic tile (6.35 mm) the ballistic limit increased linearly with the composite backing plate thickness. This occurred until the backing plate thicknesses were between 5 and 7 mm, where an abrupt local increment in the relationship (kink effect) was observed. From that zone, the ballistic limit increases linearly with the backing plate thickness. This effect has been observed for metallic backing plates as well.

Although the ballistic behaviour of this type of armour is not completely understood, there are some analytical models available for design purposes. Recently, Hetherington and Rajagopalan [29] reassessed, for mixed ceramic/composite armours, a previous model developed by Florence [30] for estimating the ballistic limit of ceramic tiles backed by a metallic plate. They assumed that the projectile residual velocity in a perforation case can be calculated as the difference between the striking velocity and the ballistic limit determined according to Florence's model. Thus, the residual kinetic energy of the projectile can be estimated using the original projectile mass. Although the theoretical bases of the model, and thus its application to the case of composite backing plates, are not very clear because of the different mechanical behavior of metallic and composite materials, such a model has been successfully used in a practical armour design problem [31], against 7.62 NATO projectiles, of a ceramic/composite plate added to a flexible armour able to defeat 9 mm Pb. and 0,357 Magnum projectiles, as will be shown in a separate paper of this Conference [32].

Regarding full-numerical analyses of impact on composite material problems, a wide bibliography is available for the low impact velocity regime but unfortunately this does not occur for the high velocity regime. Two possibilities are available for the numerical treatment of impact problems on composite materials: the micro and macro-mechanical approaches. In the first, the fibres and resin are considered independently of one another and are modelled in detail. In the second approach, the micro-structure of the composite material is not modelled and the composite plate is considered to behave as an orthotropic plate. Of course the micro-mechanical approach needs a great computer storage and takes a lot of computer time, whereas the macro-mechanical approach saves computer time although it gives less information. The latter has been used successfully by Shah et al. [33]. In both impact regimes, the problem has an intrinsic three-dimensional character because of the stress and strain fields generated in the vicinity of the impacted zone. Most of the computer codes to analyze this kind of problem use a two-dimensional plate approach and thus do not consider the influence of the through-thickness normal stress. Another important fact that suggests the convenience of a fully three-dimensional treatment of this problem is the inherent anisotropic behaviour of composite materials. Other three-dimensional analyses of the problem such as those carried out by Kuppasamy and Reddy [34] and Lee et al. [35] do not define the damage zone size in the composite. A full three-dimensional analysis computer code in which delamination zones are taken into account was developed by Wu [36,37] for unidirectionally reinforced composites. His analyses only applies when the impactor does not penetrate the surface of the plate, so it is applicable to low velocity impact regime. The assumed contact force between the impactor and the composite plate is that given by the Hertzian contact law. He considers that, although impact damage under impact load can take the forms of delamination, matrix cracking and fibre breakage, the first is of primary importance because it can reduce the mechanical strength of the composite material. Several well stated failure criteria, including the Tsai-Wu criteria for both two and three dimensional situations,

were assumed for the composite material to estimate the size of the damaged zone. The authors [37] recognized that these criteria were not meant to predict delamination under impact loading; they provided a new delamination model which suggests that delamination effect is primarily due to the tensile stress out of the plane of the laminate. However, this delamination criterion is not supported by Joshi and Sun [38] who established the role of the transverse shear stresses on matrix crack initiation. Subsequently, Peck et al. [39] modified the transient finite element method computer code developed by Wu [36] to incorporate woven fabric reinforced composites into the program although no damage criterion was adapted to this type of composite.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Despite the wide field covered in this paper, a set of general conclusions can be drawn:

a) Considerable experimental work on the impact behaviour of composite materials has been carried out, most of it concerned with the low velocity impact regime. Less has been done on composite material behaviour at high strain rates. Fibre properties are strain rate dependent and normally they behave as viscoelastic materials. Experimental tensile devices such as the Split Hopkinson bar offer promising possibilities although more work is required on the subject.

b) Analytical approaches in modelling impact on fabrics and composites are promising because they allow a variety of parametric analyses. However, analytical methods often involve rough assumptions and simplifications which can lead to non-realistic solutions. This can be avoided by paying particular attention to the phenomenology of the impact event, and trying to incorporate such kind of description into the model. But these tools should not be overlooked in designing composite materials to be subjected to impact loading.

c) Full-numerical analyses are an attractive tool to analyze impact loading on composites, but they are not well developed for problems involving impact at high velocity. The finite element method application could show the main features of this kind of problem, but it should be used together with experimental work to validate the hypotheses involved in the numerical analysis. Also, the important computer time needed to run any analysis makes them inappropriate for carrying out parametric analyses. Nevertheless more work would have to be devoted to this subject.

References

1. Stewart, I.F., *The use of kevlar on aero-engine fan containment casings*, Impact loading and dynamic behaviour of Materials, DGM Informationsgesellschaft, Vol. 2, 1988.
2. Li, Y., Ruiz, C., Harding, J., *Modelling of the response of fibre-reinforced composites*, Technomic Publ. Co., Inc..
3. Morrison, C., Bader, M.G., *Behaviour of aramid fibre yarns and composite under transverse impact*, 1st. ECCM, 1985, pp. 707-712.
4. Greszczuk, L. B. *Damage in composite materials due to low velocity impact*, Chapter 3 of *Impact Dynamics*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1982, pp. 55-94.
5. Shivakumar, K.N., Elber, W., Illg, W., *Prediction of impact force and duration due to low-velocity impact on circular composite laminates*, J. Appl. Mech., Vol. 52, 1985, pp. 674-680.
6. Hong, S., Liu, D., *On the relation between impact energy and delamination area*, Exp. Mech., Vol. 29, 1989, pp. 115-120.
7. Sjöblom, P., Hartness, J., Cordell, T. M., *On low-velocity impact testing of composite materials*, J. Comp. Mat., Vol. 22, 1988, pp.30-52.
8. Cristescu, N., Malvern, L.E., Sierakowski, R.L., *Failure mechanisms in composite plates impacted by blunt-ended penetrators*, ASTM STP 568, 1975, pp. 159-172.

9. Cantwell, W.J., Morton, J., *Comparison of the low and high velocity impact response of CFRP, Composites*, Vol. 20, 1989, pp. 545-551.
10. Takeda, N., Sierakowski, R.L., Malvern, L.E., *Microscopic observation of cross sections of impacted composite laminates*, *Comp. Tech. Rev.*, Vol. 4, 1982, pp. 4-10.
11. Takeda, N., Sierakowski, R.L., Malvern, L.E., *Transverse cracks in glass/epoxy cross-ply laminates impacted by projectiles*, *J. Materials*, Vol. 19, 1987, pp. 51-66.
12. Takeda, N., Sierakowski, R.L., Ross, C.A., Malvern, L.E., *Delamination-crack propagation in ballistically impacted glass/epoxy composite laminates*, *Experimental Mech.*, Vol. 22, 1982, pp. 19-25.
13. Takeda, N., Sierakowski, R.L., Malvern, L.E., *Wave propagation experiments on ballistically impacted composite laminates*, *J. Comp. Mater.*, Vol. 15, 1981, pp. 157-174.
14. Joshi, S.P., Sun, C.T., *Impact induced fracture in a laminated composite*, *J. Comp. Mat.*, Vol. 19, 1985, pp. 51-66.
15. Liu, D., Malvern, L.E., *Matrix cracking in impacted glass/epoxy plates*, *J. Comp. Mater.*, Vol. 21, 1987, pp. 594-609.
16. Zhu, G., Goldsmith, W., Dharan, C.K.H., *Penetration of laminated kevlar by projectiles -I. Experimental investigation*, *Int. J. Solids Structures*, Vol. 29, 1992, pp. 399-420.
17. Roylance, D., *Ballistics of transversely Impacted Fibers*, *Textile Journal*, Vol. 47, 1977, pp. 679-684.
18. Roylance, D., Wang, W.W., *Penetration mechanics of textile structures: influence of non-linear viscoelastic relaxation*, *Polymer Engng. Sci.*, Vol. 28, 19978, pp. 1068-1072.
19. Vinson, J.R., Zukas, J.A., *On the ballistic impact of textile body Armor*, *J. Appl. Mech.*, 1975, pp. 263-268.
20. Leech, C.M., Adeyefa, B.A., *Dynamics of cloth subject to ballistic impact velocities*, *Computers and Structures*, Vol. 15, 1982, pp. 423-432.
21. Roylance, D., *Influence of fibre properties on ballistic penetration of textile panels*, *Fibre Science and Technology*, Vol. 14, 1981, pp. 183-190.
22. Roylance, D., *Stress wave propagation in fibres: effect of crossovers*, *Fibre Science and Technology*, Vol. 13, 1980, pp. 385-395.
23. Zhurkov, S.N., *Kinetic concept of the strength of solids*, *Int. J. Fracture Mech.*, Vol. 1, 1965, p. 311.
24. Cunniff, P.M., *An analysis of the system effects in woven fabrics under ballistic impact*, *Textile Res. J.*, Vol. 62, 1992, pp. 495-509.
25. Zhu, G., Goldsith, W., Dharan, C.K.H., *Penetration of laminated kevlar by projectiles- II. Analytical model*, *Int. J. Solids Structures*, Vol. 29, 1992, pp. 421-436.
26. Parga, B., *Modelización de materiales compuestos a altas velocidades de deformación*, Ph. Thesis, Polytechnic University of Madrid, 1988.
27. Dupont Company, *A guide to designing and preparing ballistic protection of Kevlar*, 1983.
28. Mayselless, M., Goldsmith, W., Virostek, S. P., Finnegan, S. A., *Impact on ceramic targets*, *J. Appl. Mech.*, Vol. 54, 1987, pp. 373-378.

29. Florence, A.L., *Interaction of projectiles and composite armour plate II*. Stanford Research Institute, AMMRG-CR-69-15, 19969.
30. Hetherington, J.G., Rajagolapan, B.P., *An investigation into the energy absorbed during ballistic perforation of composite armours*, Int. J. Impact Engng., Vol. 11, 1991, pp. 33-40.
31. Navarro, C., Martínez, M.A., Cortés, R., Sánchez-Gálvez, V., *Some observations on the normal impact on ceramic faced armours backed by composite plates*, Int. J. Impact Engng. Vol. 13, 1993, pp. 145-156.
32. Martínez, Cortés R., Murillo, N., Sánchez-Gálvez, V., Navarro, C., *Impact behaviour of ceramic faced armours backed by composite plates*, Proc. ICCM 9, 1993.
33. Shah, S., Li, R.K.Y., Harding, J., *Modelling of the impact response of fibre-reinforced composite*, O.U.E.L. report, No. 1706/87, 1987.
34. Kuppusamy, T., Reddy, J.N., *A three-dimensional nonlinear analysis of cross-ply rectangular composite plates*, Computers and Structures, Vol. 18, 1984, pp. 263-272.
35. Lee, J.D., Du, S., Liebowitz, *Three dimensional finite element and dynamic analysis of composite laminate subjected to impact*, Computers and Structures, Vol. 19, 1984, pp. 807-813.
36. Wu, H-Y. T., *Impact damage of composites*, Ph. D. Thesis, Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Stanford University, 1986.
37. Wu, H-Y. T., Springer, G. S., *Impact induced stresses, strains and delaminations in composite plates*, J. Comp. Mat., Vol. 22, 1988, pp. 533-560.
38. Joshi, S.P., Sun, C.T., *Impact induced fracture in a laminated composite*, J. Composite Mat., Vol. 19, 1985, pp. 51- 66.
39. Peck, S.O., Springer, G.S., Foote, A.L., Jeske, D.H., *Impact damage in thick laminated plates, Impact loading and dynamic behaviour of Materials*, DGM Informationsgesellschaft, Vol. 1, 1988.

METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES: BEHAVIOUR

